

Kirigami –induced structural deformation in CNT: A molecular dynamics study

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Abstract

The exploration for mechanical metamaterials with desired properties is of great interest in improvement and development of advanced technology. Here, inspired by the kirigami arts, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) mechanical metamaterials are hypothetically constructed. Using classic molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, a systemic study of elastic limit, extensibility and yield stress of as-generated CNTs Kirigami (CNT-k) is performed. One designated kirigami pattern is implemented and it is shown that CNT-k typically exhibits three distinct deformation stages, where the first stage called as geometry deformation contributes quite high proportion of the ductility. Various geometric parameters of the CNT-k affecting the mechanical properties are discussed. CNT-k with specifically identical geometrical parameters presents distinct mechanical characteristics. This study provides an in-depth understanding on the effect of geometry on ductility and mechanical characteristics of CNT-K based materials.

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1. Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), a typical one-dimensional (1D) material, have attracted many interests due to unique mechanical, electrical and thermal properties, etc., in the past two decades. In mechanics, the tensile strength and Young modulus of individual CNT were predicted to be 100-200 GPa and 1-2TPa,^[1-5] respectively, which are attributed to its steady hexagonal network structures composed of strong sp^2 carbon-carbon bonds. So far, the excellent mechanical properties of CNTs have been validated by some experiments.^[6-10] For example, Yu et al. reported that the Young's modulus of individual single-walled CNTs is around 1TPa by an in situ tensile testing.^[7] Although the CNTs were generally seen as the strongest nanomaterials in nature, however, the tensile strain of CNTs are small with a range from 5.3 - 17.5%,^[7,11-13] limiting its further applications.

Recently, kirigami arts has been employed to obtain high elasticity and ductility of nanomaterials. Previously, kirigami is used in micro-scale conventional bulk materials^[14-16] by using standard top-down techniques. With the aid of optical lithography, this kirigami technology can be used in nano-scale materials. For some examples, a new nanostructure of graphene, graphene nanoribbons kirigami (GNR-k), has been cut from a polycrystalline graphene.^[17] Classic molecular dynamics (MD) simulations demonstrated that the GNR-k structures with some regular patterns can lead to a ductility behavior.^[18] Subsequently, a similar structure like GNR-k, MoS₂-kirigami, has been also hypothetically created.^[19] It was found that, by MD simulations, the kirigami pattern significantly enhance the tensile ductility of monolayer MoS₂, which is similar to that of GNR-k, even MoS₂ is a tri-layered atomic structure and has much higher bending modulus.

In this study, we employed the concept of kirigami arts to build CNTs mechanical metamaterials. To investigate CNT-based metastructures and their effects on tensile mechanical behaviors, the deformation analysis of CNT-k is carried out by using a classic MD simulation. We believe that desirable CNT-k with enhanced elasticity and ductility may open up interesting opportunities in coupling to other unique properties of CNTs.

2. Modeling and Method

In order to obtain a CNT metamaterials (CNT-k), a typical (200,200) CNT with diameter of approximately 27nm is used. The CNT-k is generated by periodically cutting out holes from three-dimensional (3D) along lattice of CNT. It is noted that this differs from GNR-k and MoS₂-k that are created by cutting out holes from two-dimensional (2D) planar structures. Moreover, one typical hole in a CNT is designedly adopted, which is in consistent with geometrical hole in GNR-k and MoS₂-k. By flattening the curved 3D holes of CNT-k, the planar hole is square in shape. Based on the geometries of holes, Square-CNT kirigami (SCK) is named.

As shown in Figure 1, right atomic structure represents unit cell replicated in a circle. Those unit cells in planar state are defined according to height $2b$ and width L . The edged carbon atom of holes in MD models is not saturated by employments of hydrogen atoms. The representative kirigami structure in Figure 1 is composed of 53256 carbon atoms, with structural parameters of $L \sim 16 \text{ \AA}$ and $b \sim 60.59 \text{ \AA}$, respectively. Different geometry parameters used in this study are shown in Table 1. The kirigami models consist of three complete unit cells along loading direction. Periodic boundary condition (PBC) is applied along the tensile direction, which can offer unconstrained ends, so that eliminating any spurious end effects during deformations, while the perimeters of the simulation boxes are free to simulate stand-alone SCK. It is noted that there are some cases where overlapping occurs under some geometrical parameters. The overlapping means that holes in SCK projected on the xy -plane are overlapped. Therefore, a parameter λ is defined to quantitatively illustrate this case:

$$\lambda_{ock} = \frac{3L - 2b}{2} \quad (1)$$

Overlapping happens when $\lambda < 0$, and in turn, when $\lambda > 0$, there is no overlapping. It should be noted that, unlike the case of graphene and MoS_2 kirigami where ribbon length is one of key parameters to the mechanical properties,^[18,19] axial length of SCK has no effect on the deformation properties due to the PBC in the axial direction.

Table 1. Geometry parameters for all studied SCK

$b(\text{\AA})$	60.59, 84.823, 141.37
$L(\text{\AA})$	6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 20, 30, 40, 50, 55, 60, 70, 75, 80, 90, 100, 110

Figure 1 Schematic of the CNT kirigami, with key geometric parameters labeled. Far right image represents unit cells replicated in a circle.

All classic MD simulations were performed to study the mechanical properties of SCK using the large-scale atomic/molecular massively parallel simulator (LAMMPS) with the second generation Reactive Bond Order (REBO) empirical potential.^[20-21] Some studies have shown that the REBO potential can accurately describe various carbon-based interactions, including bond breaking and reforming in hydrocarbon systems. To avoid the spurious strengthening effect and the nonphysical part in the tensile fracture process of SCK, the cutoff distance in REBO forcefield is set to be 0.2nm, as suggested by reference[22]. The MD simulations are performed as follows. Before loading, the kirigami structures are first quasi-statically relaxed to a local minimum configuration with using the conjugate gradient method. Subsequently, a relaxation is carried out with a sufficient simulation time of 10 ps. During the relaxation process, the lengths of as-created SCK are allowed to shrink or expand at zero pressure in the axial direction under NPT (constant number of atoms N , constant pressure P , and constant temperature T) ensemble. A time step of 0.001 ps with the velocity-Verlet integration algorithm is used in all MD simulations. The relaxed SCK are then deformed in tension by uniformly rescaling the axial coordinate of all atoms in every 1000 time steps. A strain rate of 0.005/ps is used. During the elongating process, the deformed SCK is allowed to subject to a Poisson contraction in the transverse direction of the tensile direction. The tensile forces were calculated according to the virial stress tensor components on every atom. The engineering stress is defined as

$$\sigma_x = \frac{1}{V_0} \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varepsilon_x} \quad (2)$$

$$V_0 = \pi \left[(r_0 + t/2)^2 - (r_0 - t/2)^2 \right] L_{z0} = \pi t (r_0 - t) L_{z0} \quad (3)$$

where U is the strain energy, V_0 is the initial volume of the system, r_0 and L_{z0} are the radius and the axial length of the relaxed CNT kirigami, respectively, and t is the thickness of CNT (0.34nm).^[23] The atomic stress of individual carbon atoms in the SCK is calculated by the following equation,

$$\sigma_{ij}^p = \frac{1}{\Omega^p} \left(\frac{1}{2} m^p v_i^p v_j^p + \sum_{\beta=1,n} r_{pq}^j f_{pq}^i \right) \quad (4)$$

Where p and q are the atomic indices, respectively; i and j denote indices in the Cartesian coordinate system; m^p and v^p denote the mass and velocity of atom p , respectively; Ω denotes the atomic volume of atom p ; f_{pq}^i denotes the i -component of the force between atoms p and q , respectively. And r_{pq} is the distance between atom p and q . The stress on each atom is averaged over the last latter 500 time steps of the relaxation period. The global stress of the system is then obtained by summing the stress on each atom. In addition, we simulated

pristine single-walled CNT with no holes as a comparison. The calculated fracture strains (0.27), fracture stress (114 GPa) are agreement with those in the experimental^[7, 13] and theoretical studies^[24].

3. Results and Discussion

The stress-strain curves of SCK with geometrical parameters of $a=14.14$ nm, $L= 0.8$ nm are shown in Figure 2. Three major stages of deformation for three types of SCK can be identified, as separated by regions with different color in Figure 2, where the geometry deformation stage (G-Stage, green region), elastic deformation stage (E-Stage, blue region), fracture deformation stage (F-Stage, yellow region) are denoted, respectively. During the G-stage, the global tensile stress is nearly zero, which is incomparable with that of defect-free CNT. In the E-Stage where the tensile strain exceeds approximately 35%, the tensile stress significantly increases as the strain is applied. However, the tensile strain in this stage is limited to around 15%. The ultimate tensile strength of SCK is about 1.1 GPa at the end of the E-stage. Mechanical response that markedly differs from that of G-stage is due to a change in deformation mechanisms. The last F-stage corresponds to rupture process of highly stretched SCK. As the applied tensile strains exceed a critical value, global tensile stresses drop sharply, indicating a rapid fracturing propagation.

Figure 2 Stress-strain curves of SCK metamaterials. Three distinct deformation stages which are respectively painted to green, blue and orange colors are identified.

Figure 3 Development of cross-sectional motifs of SCK subjected to axial tension strain where atoms are rendered based on their values of Poisson's ratio.

Cross-sectional motif significantly changes with applied tensile strain as shown in Figure 3, indicating disparate local Poisson's ratio. Atomic Poisson's ratio in the three SCK structures is defined as

$$v_i = -\frac{d_i^c - d_{i0}^c}{d_{i0}^c} / \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

where v_i and ε are the Poisson's ratio of i -atom and the global tensile strain, respectively. d_{i0}^c and d_i^c are the projective distances in x - y plane between i -atom and the position of center of mass of the studied system at tensile strains of zero and ε , respectively.

Figure 3 shows cross-sectional snapshots of SCK structures with three different deformation levels, in which atoms are colored according to the values of Poisson's ratios. It is observed that originally circular shaped cross-sections of SCK changes to pretty motifs, depending on magnitude of applied tensile strain. As is observed, morphology of cross-section of SCK keeps round, then complicatedly flower-like and finally to circular motif with increasing of strain prior to failure. It is interesting that notably local negative Poisson's ratios appear at the very early G-stage. Those findings are mainly attributed to distinct movements of connect nanoribbons as axial strain is forced.

Moreover, global Poisson's ratios of all the SCK are also calculated and shown in Figure 4 when the structures are the most elastic deformed. Due to different changes in the lateral width in the x - and y -directions, Poisson's ratios in the x - and y -directions are calculated and named as $v_{x/z}$ and $v_{y/z}$, respectively. Results show that Poisson's ratios of SCK vary from -3 to 32. It is also found bigger b can result in higher Poisson's ratio and L also plays an important role on the Poisson's ratio: both $v_{x/z}$ and $v_{y/z}$ significantly decrease with increasing of L .

High Poisson's ratios in SCK with small L is mainly attributed to large decreasing in area of cross-section and small elastic tension deformation.

Figure 4 Influence of geometrical parameter L on Poisson's ratio (xz and yz) with b ranging from 60.59 \AA – 141.37 \AA .

Having identified the deformation characteristics of SCK, the control over the deformation by systematically varying the geometrical parameters of kirigami unit-cell is investigated. Relationship between geometrical parameters and mechanical characteristics is a key knowledge for experimenters to design SCK metamaterials with a desired combination of mechanical properties. Figure 5 presents the relationships between the yield strain (yield stress) and geometrical parameter L of SCK. It should be noted that absence of some data points in some curves is due to the inaccessible values of geometrical parameters for generating SCK.

Figure 5 Influence of geometrical parameter L on yield strain and yield stress for SCK with different b ($b = 60.59$, 84.823 and 141.37 \AA).

Figures 5 the relationships between yield stress and yield strain and geometrical parameter L for SCK

structure with different b . It is observed that SCK structure with small L exhibits high yield strain. As an example, reduction of around 90% in the yield strain is noted when L changes from 6 Å to 110 Å. This is because when L is small, there is overlapping occurring ($\lambda < 0$) between neighboring interior holes in SCK so that G-Stage can be pretty long. It is also found that yield strain increase as b increases. This is due to that geometry deformation becomes more critical when b becomes larger.

Similarly, yield stress of SCK structures is highly depended on both the geometrical parameter b and L ; SCK structure with large L exhibits high yield stress. As an example, approximately 95% increase in yield stress of SCK structure is achieved when the magnitude of geometrical parameter L increases from around 6 to 75 Å. Parameter L plays an important role on the yield stress in SCK structure which is in consistent with the known facts that an increased width of connect necks generally makes the structure more rigid and imparts a higher critical yield load. However, when L is small, width L of connect nanoribbons plays a negligible role. It is due to that bond breaking of SCK preferentially happens at the corners in square holes because of their high stress-concentration. When L increases, λ becomes bigger than zero which means non-overlapping occurring between neighboring connect nanoribbons. And connect nanoribbons can bend to resist more applied tensile load. It can also be observed that yield stress gets higher with bigger b . The main reason can be explained as follows. Smaller b represents more holes around a circle with a given radius, implying that there exist more connect nanoribbons bending to resist the applied tensile load in SCK structure. Overall, parameter b and L have significantly impact on both yield strain and yield stress.

Figure 6 Influence of ratio of L on Young's modulus for the three types of SCK with b ranging from 60.59 Å – 141.37Å.

Apart from the yield strain and yield stress, the Young's modulus of all the SCK are also calculated. Figure 6 shows the relationships between Young's modulus and L with various b , where the Young's modulus is achieved through linear fitting of the stress-strain curves. As presented in Figures 6, SCK shows comparable Young's modulus, with values ranging from around 0.4 MPa to 550 GPa, strongly depending on the geometry parameters of L and b . Similar to other mechanical properties (yield stress and yield strain), the Young's modulus of SCK highly correlates with L ; the Young's modulus dramatically increases with increasing of L . For a given L , the Young's modulus also significantly increases as b increases. Most of kirigami structures show low Young's modulus (< 10 GPa). This is attributed to markedly low stress load in the G-stage as shown in Figure 2. However, few SCK with large L exhibit high Young's modulus that is comparable that of perfect CNT (around 812 GPa in our calculation).

Conclusion

In summary, we employed classical MD simulations to systematically study mechanical properties of hypothetical Square-CNT-kirigami. The results show that as-designed SCK are able to achieve high ductility mainly thanks to large geometrical deformation mechanism. Geometrical deformation mainly contains flip, rotation and bending of connect nanoribbon during the stretching process, resulting in pretty evolution of cross-sectional motifs and distinct local Poisson's ratio. Highly stretched SCK ultimately frustrates as result of fracturing at the high stress-concentration junctions. It is also found that geometrical parameter of holes in SCK have great effects on their ductility, tensile strength, Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus.

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